

**DIFFERENT CHARACTERISTICS OF MODALITY IN LITERARY
WORKS**

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Abstract: The current article discusses the different features of modal meaning represented in literary texts. The aim of the research is to determine specific peculiarities of modality as it shows the attitude of writer to the situation and modal markers, types of modal meanings and its usage in context. The types of modality are overviewed with the help of analytical and descriptive methods by analysis of the novel “David Copperfield” by Ch. Dickens. The results of the analysis indicate that modality can be expressed with different modal markers like: modal verbs, adjectives while author describes the action or hero, stylistic devices, with hidden or direct definitions. All in all, the usage of the types of modality: subjective and objective, explicit and implicit, epistemic, dynamic and others are explored deeply in given context.

Keywords: modality, modal verbs, epistemic, dynamic, boulomaic, subjective, modal device, literary text, author’s attitude

Introduction

Modality in text is expressed not only with words but also elements, colors and behaviors of the heroes. Therefore, the task for the analyzers of the text modality is investigating words and special definitions which indicate reader the author’s attitude to the occasion. The greatest diversity of representation of markers subjective modality, this text demonstrates in the sphere of clarifying the emotional shades of attitude to what is happening.

Methods and Materials

Charles Dickens was one of the most famous English novelists of the 19th century. He wrote most of his works about English society and lifestyle during the time which he lived. The novel “David Copperfield” is about the life of the main hero David and

the events are told by him. The novel informs the reader about social and gender issues in 19th century and it is drawn by different characters and situations. Moreover, the writer represented the child work and discrimination by adults.

Results and Discussions

This novel represents to the reader the social problems of the English society. Author's attitude to the events is described by **subjective modality**. Subjective modality is activated by descriptive words and content. For instance, David's happy life finishes when he was 7 years old. The boy describes it with his new father's (step father's) coming to their house. And the author described Mr. Murdstone as black-haired gentleman, his dog also was black, he frowns at me, his dresses and hat also was black. This description draws a portrait of unpleasant and frightening person which hates from kids. Obviously, these descriptions hint to the characteristics of that gentleman and makes reader feel darkness about him.

Similarly, the same expression is given to the sister of Mr. Murdstone who came to their house and stayed to live with them. The author described the first appearance of Mrs Murdstone as follows: She was dressed all in black and she had black hair and eyes like his brother.

The modal meaning is opened with the favor of descriptive words. This is also **subjective modality** which is frequently addressed in fictional texts. Additionally, the phrases of Ms. Murdstone to David's mom when she moved to their house reveals her personality more deeply: "I'll be looking after the house now, you are too pretty and too impractical." Here the author reports the reader how bossy and selfish Murdstones who came to David's house and began acting as the hostess. Unfortunately, his mom was so naive, weak and unsteady that she couldn't even reject their words: "My mother's eyes filled with tears, but she nodded her head".

Author utilized the **conjunction** 'but' to show the contrast in the feelings of the heroin. This modalizer expresses that she cried, it tells that she was upset and didn't want to do what they said. But she had to obey them.

Moreover, the boy's reaction to the man is given with one exact statement which makes clear to the reader his and writer's attitude to Mr. Murdstone: 'I don't want to see him.' This sentence expresses 7 years old boy's negative feelings to his stepfather and the modal meaning is represented by stative verb want. The negative grammatical category of auxiliary verb don't. Here we can see **boulomaic modality** which expresses the desire and intentions of the hero.

The category of linguistic modality conducts and directs any communicative utterance, starting with an interjection speech act and ending this utterance with a full-fledged text. For example: "Oh Davy, Davy", said my mother sadly." In this expression the interjection Oh is utilized to reflect how her mother's pain was deep and how helpless was she to help him. Furthermore, the stylistic device repetition is used as **modal device** to reinforce the modal meaning in the text.

It is stated that, modality expresses the possibility or the necessity of happening events from the point of the heroes which is hinted by the author.

"After that, I fell asleep. Mr. Barkis and his horse were taking me as far as Yarmouth. There, I must wait in the inn, for the coach to London. "

In this part of the novel, the boy is explaining the situation when he was sent to school situated in London as a punishment for biting from his step father's hand when he hit him with belt. So in this passage the boy is thinking about the possible events which are waiting for him on the way to London. It is expressed with modal auxiliary must which is usually addressed in **epistemic modality**. Epistemic modality mostly shows the author's attitude to the possibility of happening events. In addition, the phrase after that which is given in the beginning of the text expresses **dynamic modality** as it shows the circumstances of happening events.

Another example for **modality of possibility** is represented in the dialogue between David and the carrier Mr. Barkis: "Someone wants to marry her, perhaps?" The reader can see here the adverbial modalizer perhaps which reflects **epistemic modality** showing possibility of the event. Here the events take part in the carriage and the boy was talking to Mr. Barkis about Peggotty, a lady, who served at their home. He

gave the carrier the cookies which was baked by Peggotty. The other type of the modality which is utilized here is **boulomaic modality** with the verb want. After that, Mr. Barkis began giving several questions about her and the author gave description to Peggotty with boy's word:

“Did she make them?” Mr. Barkis asked.

- Oh, yes, - I said. – She makes our cakes and does all the cooking. She is a very good cook.”

Here the writer utilized **subjective modality** to indicate his attitude to Peggotty. It is obviously seen from the discussions that she is a good servant, housekeeper and of course, can be good wife ever. The phrase very good cook reveals that is not only about cooking, but also about being a good person. Undoubtedly, the reader can see that she is the only person who was nearby him in all situations and even helped to take after his children. The author used **lexical modal** meaning here.

David lived in several places, worked after mother's death and searched for her aunt Betsy Trotwood after all. When he came to her house and the view is told by him as follows:

“We were soon walking on soft grass. Then I saw a pretty little house, with a garden in front of it.” The boy is describing aunt's house with the phrass pretty, little, with a garden represents the image of small and cozy home from the eyes of the boy. The author revealed his attitude with **subjective modality** to indicate how the boy feels to be there.

Moreover, the reader can feel the author and his image in this novel as the author speaks with the boy's words. This very fact, makes the author be in the center of the events.

David stayed in that little pleasant house with her aunt from father's side. He didn't sleep in peace for the last few years and the first night at that house is described as follows: “I was feeling very sleepy now. Someone put me on a coach very gently and covered me with a shawl. As I closed my eyes, I heard my aunt's voice. ‘Poor boy, poor little boy’, she said. Warm and happy, I was soon asleep “. This text activates the

inner position of the hero with the explicit definition. Poor little Davy had to work after his mother's death and never felt happy again. Author's attitude can be obviously seen from the words happy and warm and activates subjective modality in this passage.

After becoming grown up, David acquainted with several people and he lived under the control and help of his aunt Ms. Betsy Trotwood. And he fell in love with a girl who was a daughter of his master. The author described Dora with the words of Aunt Betsy and stylistic device **simile** is utilized to reflect modal meaning in the text.

“- I know that I love Dora,” – I replied. “I love her with all my heart.” “- She is very pretty; I suppose?” – my aunt asked.

“- She is beautiful!” I said. “My Dora is the most beautiful girl in the world! She has the prettiest curly hair and the sweetest smile that I have ever seen.” My aunt turned her head away. “I remember your father saying the same about your dear, silly mother,” she said quietly. “Dora isn't silly,” I said quickly... My aunt smiled sadly. “Young and blind” she whispered.”

As it is mentioned above, the author represents Dora in comparison with David's mom. Aunt Betsy considered that she looks like his mother saying the words the same silly as your dear mother. Furthermore, this **subjective modality** reveals the characteristics of Dora totally. Even though the author is not telling it explicitly, the reader can understand from the aunt's words that she is weak, helpless and too young like David's mother. Another modal meaning is represented with the word suppose which indicates the possibility and it activates **epistemic modality**.

Moreover, a word blind is a **metaphor** and it means being blind from love not the exact physical blindness. This expression represents the author's attitude to David's love to Dora like he is in love with her as a blind and can't see her real personal characteristics. This **lexical modality** hints that this love has no further future and it is proved during the sequences of events in the novel. Dora was not good wife and was really young, impractical to go through the family issues and became ill after all. She couldn't recover from illness and died then as like David's mother.

So, when the discussion goes about David's personal life, it is worth to state one important hero of the novel – Miss Agnes, the daughter of the lawyer who was private barrister of David's aunt. Totally, she was one of bosom-friends of Davy and it is not told openly about Agnes' feelings to David, hence there are numerous hints which indicate her attitude to him. For instance,

“You are more than a sister to me, Agnes. You know how much I love you. Your love would be a great gift to any man. Do not give it to him.’

Agnes looked at me. Her eyes were full of love. Then she smiled. – I shall never marry to Uriah Heep, - she said.”

Here **subjective modality** is utilized to express author's evaluation to the relationship of Agnes and David. Author doesn't explicitly tell the reader that Agnes loves him. But he shows it with the implicit information as her eyes were full of love. This expression reveals that love was for David, but he was in love with another lady and that's why she kept it secretly. Anyway, the reader can imagine the picture of a lady who looks at her loved one. However, the author points it with another hero's word who was aware of it:

“Agnes thinks that I should write to Dora's aunt and tell her my feelings,’- I said.... My aunt shook her head again. ‘Blind, so blind’, she whispered, but I didn't understand her.” In the first statement, the modal meaning is expressed with conditional verb think which determines the opinion of the heroin to the discussed event. The modal verb should activate the necessity of writing letter to Dora's aunt. This modal device belongs to **epistemic modality** and the author shows the way to the solution of their problem. Additionally, the word blind is used one more again as a modal device which comprehends metaphorical meaning as it is mentioned above.

The description about the hero Uriah Heep is another example for **subjective modality**. He was an assistant to Agnes' father and he is expressed by the author as follows: « Heep is very unpleasant and not humble at all,' I said quickly 'Why do you want to talk about him?' "I think papa is afraid of Uriah,' Agnes told me. «Heep knows everything about business now. » The image of Uriah Heep is drawn with adjectives

unpleasant, not humble and the phrase he knows everything about business. These words point at his personal characteristics. He was really sly person who cheated on s business and always used a word “humble” to define himself. Here modal meaning to his inner world is defined with the phrase he was t humble at all. And Agnes words I think papa is afraid of him reveal her attitude to that man and his father’s partnership. The modal marker is activated with the verb think.

Conclusion

The novel “David Copperfield” by Charles Dickens is analyzed and explored the usage of modality. As it was stated above, fictional texts include subjective modality which is defined by descriptive content. The analysis proved that the description of the heroes draws their portrait precisely and indicates author’s attitude completely.

Moreover, we could see from the research that the literary texts encompass not only subjective modality, but also other types of the modality according to the confidence, possibility, non-confidence of the author. For example, in this part of the novel, the boy is explaining the situation when he was sent to school situated in London as a punishment for biting from his step father’s hand when he hit him with belt. So in this passage the boy is thinking about the possible events which are waiting for him on the way to London. It is expressed with modal auxiliary must which is usually addressed in **epistemic modality**. Epistemic modality mostly shows the author’s attitude to the possibility of happening events. In addition, the phrase after that which is given in the beginning of the text expresses **dynamic modality** as it shows the circumstances of happening events.

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